

Review Protocol: Benzotriazole in cancer: preclinical evidence and structure–activity relationship insights

Authors

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Background

Benzotriazole derivatives have shown promising anticancer activity in preclinical studies (*in vitro* and *in vivo*); however, evidence is scattered across heterogeneous experimental models. A systematic synthesis is needed to evaluate structural classes, mechanisms of action, and methodological quality.

Objectives

1. Identify *in vitro* and *in vivo* preclinical studies on benzotriazole derivatives in cancer
2. Classify derivatives based on chemical structure
3. Summarize anticancer mechanisms
4. Assess risk of bias in included studies (*in vitro* and *in vivo*)

Eligibility Criteria

Models: *in vitro* and *in vivo* cancer models

Intervention: benzotriazole and benzotriazole derivatives

Comparators: untreated controls, positive controls such as reference anticancer drugs

Outcomes: cytotoxicity, tumor growth, toxicity, mechanisms

Study design: Original studies

Language: English only

Timeframe: January 2010 – May 2025

Exclusion Criteria

duplicates, secondary studies, studies lacking anticancer evaluation, studies based only on *in silico* analysis and articles that could not be retrieved in full.

Databases

PubMed/MEDLINE, Scopus, and Web of Science.

Search Strategy

Search terms	benzotriazole, benzotriazole derivatives, 1H-benzotriazole, in vivo, in vitro, animal model, pharmacological effect, therapeutic effect, anticancer.
Search sequences	PubMed: (benzotriazole OR benzotriazole derivatives OR 1H-benzotriazole) AND (in vivo OR "in vitro" OR "animal model" OR "pharmacological effect" OR "therapeutic effect" OR anticancer) Filters: Search field (title/abstract); Article language (English) WOS: (benzotriazole OR benzotriazole derivatives OR 1H-benzotriazole) AND (in vivo OR "in vitro" OR "animal model" OR "pharmacological effect" OR "therapeutic effect" OR "anticancer") Filters: Search field (topic); Language (English) Scopus: (benzotriazole OR benzotriazole derivatives OR 1H-benzotriazole) AND (in vivo OR "in vitro" OR "animal model" OR "pharmacological effect" OR "therapeutic effect" OR anticancer) Filters: Search within (article title, abstract and keywords); Language (English)
Databases searched	PubMed/Medline WOS Scopus
Other sources	-
Part of journals searched	Title, abstract
Years of search	January 2010- May 2025
Language	English language only
Types of studies to be included	Original articles

Study Selection

Two reviewers independently screened titles/abstracts (G.M. and A.M.) and full texts (G.M. and A.P.). Disagreements were resolved through discussion.

Data Extraction

Data extracted included publication details, compound identifiers, experimental models, dosing, outcomes, mechanisms and toxicity. Extraction was performed by one reviewer and verified by a second (G.M. and A.M.).

Risk of Bias Assessment

In vitro studies were assessed using the QUIN tool by G.M. and A.P. In vivo studies were assessed using the SYRCLE risk-of-bias tool by G.M. and A.M.

Data Synthesis

Due to methodological heterogeneity, results were synthesized narratively and summarized in structured tables.

Protocol Registration

Prospective registration in PROSPERO was not possible because the review had already commenced. The protocol review was retrospectively registered and is available at: [10.5281/zenodo.17950716](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17950716)

Deviations from Protocol

No deviations from this protocol occurred during the conduct of the review.

Ethics

No ethical approval was required.

Dissemination

Results are intended for publication in a peer-reviewed journal.

Contributions

G.M. and A.P. conceived the review; G.M. and A.P. performed the search; G.M. and A.M. performed the initial screening; G.M. and A.P. performed the secondary screening. G.M. and A.M. extracted the data; G.M. and A.P. conducted the risk of bias for in vitro studies (QUIN tool); G.M. and A.M. conducted the risk of bias for animal studies (SYRCLE tool). All authors contributed to the conceptualization, drafting, and critical revision of the protocol and approved the final version